

Manual for the Methodology

“Consultative Ethics Review”

v.1.2

Authors: Marjo Rauhala, Matthias Kaiser, Ioannis Manos, Tina Garani-Papadatos, Hella von Unger, Maresa Berliri, Jonas Pfister, Konstantina Giouvanopoulou, Xenia Ziouvelou, Vasiliki Mollaki

Contributors: K&I srls, KIT, KUL, LM MUENCHEN, MEFST, NCSR-D, NORSUS, RUG, TUW, UB, UBO, UC, UKIM, UM, UNIWA, TUW Research Ethics Committee

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1 Introduction

This manual summarizes the approach to consultative research ethics review described in the Document “Consultative Research Ethics Review: Concept Note/Manual”. The Consultative Ethics Review is dialogic and supportive in character, its implementation requires face-to-face meetings between researchers and research ethics peer reviewers. The consultative nature of the methodology means that the process results in recommendations and suggestions of improvement in a study from the perspective of research ethics (for example, measures to improve participants’ safety). During the meeting most questions that the researchers may not have been able to address sufficiently in writing in their form for requesting review, can be immediately clarified. A typical question that is often left unanswered in application forms – as misinterpreted to be relevant only to clinical research – is the inquiry concerning potential unintended or unexpected findings in social science research.

Face-to-face meetings facilitate the dialogue between researchers and ethics committee members. The attitude adopted by the committee members is that of a “critical friend”; the members’ task is to point out the potential concerns in the proposed work while guiding the researcher to improving the research design from the perspective of research ethics.

2 Projects and applicability

- The consultative methodology is suited for research that is in the planning stages and is characterized by complexity, novelty, or unpredictability in their ethical dimensions.
- Moreover, the methodology is suited in contexts where the experience of researchers in addressing research ethical issues is evolving.
- The consultative methodology is suited for interdisciplinary research settings where researchers are using methods from other disciplines in which they are not fully trained (example: engineers involving human participants in diverse user studies, technology trials etc.)

3 Target groups

This methodology particularly addresses:

- Researchers who are conducting projects with significant or emergent ethical challenges.
- Research Ethics Committees that consider it their responsibility to provide support to researchers in identifying and addressing ethical issues beyond the traditional paper-based review, reporting, and approval.

4 Outcomes

- The approach fosters skill-development in identifying and addressing questions of research ethics within research teams, encouraging critical ethical awareness throughout the project.
- It has potential to enhance the overall quality of research outcomes by embedding ethical considerations into the entire research process from the conception and by design.

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- It contributes to broader capacity building ambitions of an institution by expanding the role of the research ethics committee to include consulting and supporting researchers in dialogue rather than focusing primarily an approval of research. In this way the vast knowledge and competence in addressing research ethics that research ethics committee have becomes more accessible in the institution.

5 Specific characteristics

Phase(s)

- This methodology applies across the entire research lifecycle, from the initial stages of project planning to the conclusion of the research (see Figure 1). In order to enable ethics-by-design, the process should start before the research design is ready for submission to a funding body.
- The methodology is suited for continued and iterated use. Researchers are encouraged to re-submit their research for a follow-up review if any new issues emerge, or, something ethically relevant changes in their research environment or context.
- In principle, the committee can also be engaged toward the end of the life cycle of the research, for example, to assess together with the researcher whether there could be any harmful effects in publishing the research results (see, Figure 2).

Weaknesses

- This approach is resource-intensive and depends on committed research ethics reviewers in the research ethics committee.
- Each submitted proposal for ethics review is allocated 40-50 minutes of discussion time in the research ethics committee's meeting. Only the ethically most sensitive proposals can be addressed in personal meetings; others will need to be reviewed in the more traditional paper-based way.
- A cultural shift within research institutions and the establishment of new procedures is necessary to fully integrate this methodology.

Strengths

- This methodology has a significant potential for sensitizing researchers to the ethical dimensions of their work. Moreover, it has potential for improving research outputs as ethical concerns have been taken into account early on and by design.
- Research Ethics Committees unfortunately do not enjoy great popularity among researchers. They are conceived as something to “get through”, even to avoid, if possible. The consultative ethics review methodology has the potential to improve the image of research ethics committees and the work they do. The dialogue between researchers and committee members takes place on an equal basis in face-to-face meetings and each party stands to mutually benefit from the process: reviewers learn about cutting edge research while

researchers learn about ways to identify and address ethical concerns in their research from the start.

- The consultative ethics review methodology may allow for greater flexibility in addressing ethical issues as they arise during the research process. It allows iterated and continued ethics review.
- This methodology clearly underlines the fact that the responsibility for addressing ethical issues and the measures to mitigate risk in a research project always remain with the researchers; this responsibility cannot be delegated to an ethics body or other experts. The approach shifts the emphasis from oversight by an external body to a sense of responsibility in the research team.

6 The Methodology at a Glance

Consultative Ethics Review

Advice by experts and/or peers to embed ethics-by-design

Figure 1. Overview of the Methodology "Consultative Ethics Review".

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Figure 2. Possible phases and foci of consultative ethics review.

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